

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Behavioral responses to value chain related policies and governance initiatives

Deliverable 5.1

Summary

Work Package	5
Deliverable N°	5.1
Dissemination Level	Public
Type	Document, Report
Lead Partner	European Forest Institute. Co-lead University of Freiburg
Due Date	30.11.2024
Submission Date	31.10.2024
Status	Final
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About CLEVER

Project Number	101060765
Project Title	CLEVER: Creating leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-15
Start date	1 st September 2022
End date	31 st August 2025
Coordinator	RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN

This document has been prepared in the framework of the project CLEVER. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the European Research Executive Agency under HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions, grant agreement n°101060765; and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10038491]

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ACRONYMS

EU	European Union
EUDR	European Union regulation on deforestation-free products
EUTR	European Union timber regulation
FAQ	Frequently asked questions
FERC	Forest and ecosystem risk commodity
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NPFD	Non-permanent forest domain
PFD	Permanent forest domain
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report examines how business actors from five focal value chains are responding to the European Union regulation on deforestation-free products (EUDR) in preparation for its implementation. These value chains are Brazil-European Union (EU) soy, timber, and wood pulp, and Cameroon-EU and Gabon-EU timber. As such, our analysis covers supply (Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon) and demand sides (the EU). First, based on secondary data sources (including TRASE database) and semi-structured key informant interviews with 13 interviewees conducted in March-July 2023, the report maps the five focal value chains, providing a contextual understanding for the analysis. Second, based on key informant interviews conducted from October 2023 to April 2024 with 200 interviewees from the different case study countries/regions along these value chains (e.g., business actors, public actors, non-governmental organizations), the report analyzes business actors' behavioral responses to the EUDR. This analysis is rooted in a theoretical framework (M8 & M11) proposing four complementary logics to explain actors' behavior: regulative logic (e.g., regulatory carrots and sticks), economic logic (e.g., market (dis)incentives), normative logic (e.g., societal norms and pressure), and cultural-cognitive logic (e.g., internal organizational values).

In all the value chains, economic reasons reportedly motivate businesses to ensure their products are compliant with the EUDR (i.e., deforestation-free and produced legally). This has to do, for instance, with the perceived high profitability of the EU market or non-EU businesses being induced by demands (i.e., the requirement for geolocations of all production plots and requests for information/documents to support due diligence processes) by businesses operating and trading in the EU market to follow the EUDR requirements. However, the EUDR was also seen as creating restrictions and economic burdens for accessing the EU market, which may lead some businesses to abandon the market. In terms of regulative motivations for compliance, businesses in the EU (who will be required to conduct due diligence to ensure that products have been produced legally and are deforestation-free) are also concerned about perceived high penalties from the EUDR in the case of non-compliance. This was of lesser concern in the supply side countries, since the EUDR does not place legal obligations on business actors there. It was also highlighted that the influence of the regulative logic could be undermined if EUDR monitoring and enforcement in the EU ended up being ineffective. Throughout the value chains, external-normative considerations also play moderately into the decision to comply with the EUDR. For instance, certain businesses (e.g., consumer-facing and large businesses and brands) are sensitive to their reputation being damaged from EUDR non-compliance, but for others such considerations may not be relevant. Organizational values can also motivate EUDR compliance but only for some businesses, such as those who have sustainability high on their internal agenda. Knowledge and understanding of the EUDR also appeared still lacking, which can hinder appropriate and informed responses to it. Thus, on the supply side,

economic logic appears to be key in explaining businesses' responses to the EUDR, with regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive logics having less prominent behavioral effects. On the demand side, regulative logic supported by economic logic is what mainly seems to motivate EUDR compliance related behavioral decisions.

The report also finds that across the value chains, businesses were preparing for EUDR implementation, such as collecting necessary information and data. Despite the fact that businesses face various challenges with fulfilling EUDR requirements (e.g., related to geolocation and traceability), they reportedly intend to comply with the new rules. Interviewees along the value chains proposed that possible adaptations to the EUDR might include simplifying their value chains (e.g., cutting out intermediaries, indirect suppliers, and small market actors), as it may be harder to obtain the required information or ensure traceability. Due to these behavioral responses, existing divisions in value chains, where some supply side market actors have access to the EU market while others are mainly connected to domestic or other export markets with lower legality and deforestation-free standards, may be reinforced.

The report concludes by noting the importance of also providing complementary positive economic incentives – currently missing in the EUDR – for non-EU businesses to maintain access to the EU market and produce EUDR compliant products. This could also help avert the risk that certain supply side market actors (e.g., small and medium-sized enterprises and smallholder producers), who face proportionally higher implementation costs and challenges, can end up being excluded from EU-bound value chains. A risk is otherwise that the EU could lose some of its market potential of leveraging positive change in supply side countries. A highly conducive development for the EUDR's implementation effectiveness in reducing tropical forest loss would further be if governments of third countries (e.g., in Asia) started raising their standards to the level of the EUDR, thus resulting in a so-called “Brussels Effect”, or regulatory “race to the top”, diffusing the advanced EUDR standards to other major demand markets. Another conducive, and perhaps more likely, development would be if some businesses in third countries started adhering to and conducting EUDR-aligned due diligence even without changes in the respective national regulatory contexts, as hinted in at least some of our findings. It will also be crucial for the EU to step up its assistance to non-EU countries (e.g., forest partnerships) to create positive (economic) incentives. Furthermore, the effectiveness of the EUDR will also depend on whether the new rules are effectively monitored and enforced in the EU and whether EU businesses follow the obligations and spirit of the regulation, particularly around supporting smallholders through capacity building and investments as part of their risk mitigation, as outlined in the EUDR (Art. 11).

By using the empirical case of business actors' responses to the EUDR, this report is meant to further contribute to the literature and understanding of how value

chain actors likely respond to policies and governance mechanisms. As such, the report seeks to generate a better understanding of the key self-reported behavioral responses and drivers of specific value chain actors to EU law inside and outside the EU and draws lessons on the potential effectiveness of EUDR implementation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Forests are vital ecosystems that provide a multitude of services, such as food, carbon storage and sequestration, climate regulation, and biodiversity (CPF, 2018). However, forests and other ecosystems (e.g., savannas), particularly in the tropics and subtropics, are under serious threat by forest and agricultural commodity production, such as soy, timber, and palm oil (Pendrill et al., 2022). Forest and biodiversity loss related to such forest and ecosystem risk commodities (FERCs) can also be associated with other negative socio-economic impacts, like human rights violations and undermined livelihoods (Buckley & Liesch, 2023).

In the period 2010–2014, 29–39% of tropical deforestation-related emissions were driven by international trade (Pendrill et al., 2019). Hence, deforestation, forest degradation, and associated biodiversity loss in one place can be “telecoupled” to consumption in another, even faraway place (Meyfroidt et al., 2013). Between these places of production and consumption, commodities are produced, processed, traded, manufactured, and sold in often complex, globalized value chains that involve multiple actors, including businesses (from small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to large multinational corporations) and actors influencing value chains indirectly, such as non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and public regulators (Boström et al., 2015).

Numerous public policies and private governance mechanisms exist at international (i.e., set at global level and concerning global issues), transnational (i.e., not set at global level but having an extraterritorial reach), and national (i.e., set at national level and applying within a country's jurisdiction) levels aiming to govern and regulate legal and/or sustainable FERC value chains across demand and supply side countries and regions (Sotirov et al., 2020; Berning et al., 2023). The policies and governance mechanisms aim to steer value chain actors' behavior through different pathways of influence (including rules, markets, norms/discourses, and knowledge – D4.2) (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012; Sotirov et al., 2020, 2022). Yet, the fact that forest loss has persisted despite the existence of policies and governance mechanisms casts doubt over their implementation and enforcement effectiveness (FAO, 2020; Sotirov et al., 2020). Indeed, actors can respond to policies and governance mechanisms in ways that *de facto* alter the impacts of these instruments on the ground, as compared to what was intended by their design. Existing research has sought to understand how value chain actors, such as businesses, respond to different public policies and private governance mechanisms (Acheampong & Maryudi, 2020; Berock & Ongolo, 2019; Boakye, 2018; Köthke, 2020; Köthke & Sotirov, 2024; Mayers et al., 2009; Nathan et al., 2018; Tegegne et al., 2022). However, there is still limited knowledge about this, particularly in the context of transnational instruments. Addressing knowledge gaps in how value chain actors respond to policies and governance mechanisms is important for informing their design and enhancing their implementation and enforcement.

Against this background, this report seeks to understand how value chain actors respond to policies and governance mechanisms regulating deforestation and forest degradation, with focus on business actors' responses to the European Union (EU) regulation on deforestation-free products (EUDR), due to its innovativeness and alleged potential to affect business actor behavior globally across multiple commodities and value chains (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; European Union, 2023). The EUDR – the application of which was originally set to begin on 30 December 2024 but in late 2024 was delayed by the EU by one year – mandates businesses in the EU to ensure that various FERCs and derived products imported to, traded in, or exported from the EU market are legally produced and free of deforestation and forest degradation. The EUDR has obligations targeted to EU businesses, who must perform due diligence and ensure that relevant products are both legally produced and deforestation-free before placing them on the EU market. Whilst the regulation does not place legal obligations on actors outside the EU, producers and suppliers in non-EU countries may need to provide certain information (e.g., geolocations of the plots where products were grown/harvested) to downstream actors for products destined for the EU market, so that EU businesses can fulfil their obligations. In terms of commodities and countries, we focus on five focal value chains as Brazil-EU soy, Brazil-EU timber, Brazil-EU wood pulp, Cameroon-EU timber, and Gabon-EU timber.

In examining business actors' behavior along the value chains in response to the EUDR, we focus here on two research questions:

1. What is the configuration of the five focal value chains?
2. How do business actors (plan to) respond to the EUDR?

By using the empirical case of business actors' stated responses to the EUDR, we aim to contribute to the broader literature and understanding of how value chain actors respond to policies and governance mechanisms.

This report is structured in two parts. Part I maps the five focal value chains, generating a contextual understanding about them. Building on this mapping, we zoom in to analyze business actors' stated behavioral responses to the EUDR in part II. Finally, we discuss and conclude.

2 OBJECTIVES

This report's specific objectives are to understand: i) the configuration of the five focal value chains, and ii) how business actors respond to the EUDR. Based on this, we aim to draw lessons for the potential effectiveness of the EUDR.

PART I – VALUE CHAIN MAPPING

We begin with a conceptual and theoretical framework focused on supply chains, supply chain mapping, and value chains. Next, a methods section introduces how the mapping of value chains was conducted. Finally, the results section presents the configuration of the five focal value chains.

3 PART I CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The flow of goods from producer to end consumer can be described as a supply chain or a value chain – the two concepts differ in their focus. A supply chain denotes the flow and transformation of goods from raw materials to end consumers, and the role of different entities (e.g., business actors) in it (Janvier-James, 2012). To make sense of their configuration, supply chains can be mapped (MacCarthy et al., 2022). The literature defines the act of supply chain mapping as “a stand-in for the actual supply chain environment, which simplifies the complex relationships to a greater degree, yet captures the essence of the environment” allowing for a “macrographic representation of the current state of supply chain” (Mubarik et al., 2023, p. 2). Correspondingly, a supply chain map is “a diagrammatic representation, providing a ‘likeness and a simplified model’ of a supply chain with both visualization and information about key features” (MacCarthy et al., 2022, p. 3).

Nodes and links are the minimum information requirements for a supply chain map (MacCarthy et al., 2022). Links represent the connectors between nodes, indicating the directional flow of material and possibly information and/or finance. Nodes are primary actors (i.e., entities that directly contribute to value-adding activities) and secondary actors (e.g., third-party logistics providers, auditors, regulators). The primary and secondary actors, combined, cover categories such as businesses and their associations, public actors, international organizations, NGOs, research/training organizations, think tanks, consultants, certification, and finance, and they can be described as value chain actors.

Value chain actors assume different stage-specific roles in the regulatory process, like implementation, monitoring, and enforcement. Businesses (producers, traders, processors, manufacturers, and retailers) as the regulated actors play an important role in the implementation of regulations due to their operational capacity, but when it comes to monitoring and enforcement, they lack independence (in case of private regulation) or authority (in case of public regulation) (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Steurer, 2013). Public actors (e.g., EU institutions and EU Member State authorities as well as state agencies in Brazil/Cameroon/Gabon) act in policy making and law enforcement functions. Hence, they cannot directly implement standards within businesses, but they possess influence when it comes to public standards setting, monitoring and enforcement, where they have main authority (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Steurer, 2013). NGOs (local and international, along the value chains) have little direct role in implementation, but they often assume watchdog roles in monitoring and possibly supporting enforcement (Abbott & Snidal, 2021). Third-party, voluntary certification actors (e.g., forest and agricultural commodity certification schemes (setting the standards) and auditing (verifying compliance)) contribute to implementation and monitoring by influencing management practices at businesses through private standards. These actors may be differently influenced

by policies and governance mechanisms, leading also to different behavioral responses.

Mapping can be done at different levels. At the macro level, global value chain maps cover whole countries and industries and map aggregated value-adding activities. At the micro level, process maps have an inter-firm and intra-firm scope and focus on process steps and information (MacCarthy et al., 2022). Supply chain maps are between the macro and micro levels at the inter-firm level, mapping value chain actors, activities, and products (MacCarthy et al., 2022).

Supply chains, which are focused on the logistics of the chain, are embedded in a broader socio-cultural and environmental context. For instance, economic activities (e.g., primary production) in the supply chain can lead to negative social and environmental externalities, like human rights violations (e.g. disputes over land ownership) and deforestation (Buckley & Liesch, 2023). Between a social foundation and an ecological ceiling lies the space that is conceptualized in the “doughnut economy” model, as alternative to conventional growth based economic model, as ecologically safe and socially just for economic activities (Raworth, 2017). The social foundation comprises 12 social dimensions drawing on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2016) and the ecological ceiling includes nine planetary boundaries critical for the environment (e.g., climate change, ocean acidification) (Richardson et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2009). Falling short on the social foundation means failing to provide the basic rights and conditions to life, while exceeding the ecological ceiling results in overshooting the pressure on Earth’s life-giving systems (Rockström et al., 2009). Sustainable supply chains could be seen as operating in a space that is ecologically safe and socially just, respecting the limits of the social foundation and the ecological ceiling.

Compared to the narrower concept of supply chain, the concept of value chain aims to integrate multiple processes shaping how commodities are produced, traded and consumed. This includes economic, social, political and environmental aspects. Value chains “encompass the organization, coordination and linkages, power dynamics, and governance between actors and as such can be used to investigate governance and identify opportunities and possible leverage points for interventions and changes in chain arrangements” (Ingram et al., 2018, p. 130). Through the incorporation of multiple values and governance aspects, the value chain concept offers a lens through which it is possible to examine problems and opportunities that are shared by different value chain actors (Clay & Feeney, 2019).

In the following section, we outline how we apply the supply chain and value chain concepts in this report.

4 PART I METHODS

We adopt the more advanced concept of value chain in what follows, going from supply chain logistics (part I) towards their social foundation, ecological ceiling, and multiple values and governance aspects (part II). We frame the value chain maps with the social foundation and ecological ceiling to highlight the boundaries of the Doughnut Economics models, within which value chains should operate. We focus on the inter-business chain of activities for specific products (i.e., soy, timber, wood pulp) (MacCarthy et al., 2022), aligned with our analytical focus. As part of the mapping, we also conduct a brief exploration of gender dimension in the focal value chains.

We selected our focal value chains (Brazil-EU soy, Brazil-EU timber, Brazil-EU wood pulp, Cameroon-EU timber, and Gabon-EU timber) as representing important supply and demand side countries/regions for these FERCs. The Amazon and the Congo Basin (Cameroon, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Republic of the Congo, Equatorial Guinea and Gabon) constitute the two largest rainforests on Earth, housing much of the planet's terrestrial biodiversity (WWF, n.d.-a, n.d.-b). Soy causes significant deforestation/ecosystem conversion and impacts on biodiversity in Brazil (Pendrill et al., 2022), including in non-forest biomes rich in biodiversity, such as the Brazilian Cerrado (Françoso et al., 2015). Soy production also often expands onto pasture, which, consequently, expands into forest (Zu Ermgassen et al., 2020). Most forest degradation is attributable to short-term disturbances like selective logging (Vancutsem et al., 2021), which is prevalent under forest concession regimes both in the Amazon and the Congo Basin (Lapola et al., 2023; Tegegne et al., 2019; Tyukavina et al., 2018), or conversion of natural forests to planted forests and plantations (Mahmoud et al., 2020). Logging, for instance, stimulates road network construction, which opens up access to forested areas (Brandt et al., 2016). Such processes of forest degradation can have negative consequences for biodiversity and increased wildfire risks (Brandt et al., 2016; Lapola et al., 2023). Further, nearly half of forest degradation is eventually succeeded by deforestation (Vancutsem et al., 2021). As a key FERC consumer region, the EU has a large role in driving the demand for various FERCs (Cuyppers et al., 2013). In 2017, the EU was responsible for 16% of deforestation associated with international trade (Wedeux & Schulmeister-Oldenhove, 2021).

To conduct the mapping, we first reviewed relevant scientific (e.g., Lescuyer et al., 2013; Worah et al., 2019) and gray (e.g., Madingou et al., 2019; Smith, 2006) literature and secondary data sources, including the Trase initiative¹ (e.g., in relation to soy) and trade statistics, to develop initial value chain maps (M10). The initial maps identified key nodes in the value chains and the links interconnecting them. Second, during March-July 2023, we conducted semi-structured key informant interviews with 13 interviewees, two of which took place

¹ <https://www.trase.earth/>

by email (Supplementary Material 1), to validate the draft value chain maps by refining the nodes and links. The interviewees included members of the CLEVER Stakeholder Reference Group. We transcribed the interviews, anonymized them, and assigned a unique ID to every interviewee (e.g., "I-n"). This anonymous interviewee ID is used when referencing analyzed data in the results.

The resulting value chain maps are presented in the following section.

5 PART I RESULTS

Table 1 below provides quantitative context for the five focal value chains. The subsequent sections describe the results of the value chain mapping in more detail.

Table 1. Overview of production and trade statistics relevant to the focal value chains.

	Forest area (1000 ha) and proportion of total land area ^a	Production quantity (t) ^a	Total exports (t) and share of production exported ^a	Total exports to the EU (t) and share of EU-bound exports of all exports ^b	Total imports by EU (1000 USD) and share of imports from source country of all imports ^b
Brazil soy	494,196 (59%)	123,645,652 ^c	99,243,728 (80%) ^d	15,266,295 (16%) ^e	31,235,676 (20%) ^e
Brazil timber		183,224,667 ^f	10,156,948 (6%) ^f	353,217 (10%) ^g	40,461,840 (1%) ^{g,h}
Brazil wood pulp		32,104,667 ⁱ	18,051,185 (56%) ⁱ	4,024,832 (23%) ^j	32,040,022 (7%) ^j
Cameroon timber	20,228 (43%)	112,991,662 ^k	1,751,832 (36%) ^k	251,734 (17%) ^l	4,985,286 (5%) ^{l,m}
Gabon timber	23,506 (91%)	1,442,240 ⁿ	1,103,327 (77%) ⁿ	129,698 (18%) ^o	4,659,581 (3%) ^{o,p}

Note: forest area in 2022, all other data is an average from 2019-2021.

^a Source: FAOSTAT (FAO, n.d.). ^b Source: ITC (International Trade Centre, n.d.). ^c Soybeans. ^d Cake of soya beans, soya bean oil, soya beans, soya sauce. ^e HS codes 1201, 120810, 210310, 210610, 230400, 350400. ^f Industrial roundwood, sawnwood, wood-based panels, fibreboard. ^g HS codes 4407, 4412, 4421, 9403. ^h Within HS4407, tree species are specified by HS codes. Only the top-3 HS codes (440729, 440711, 440799) from the "value of imports from the source country by EU" were included. ⁱ Wood pulp, paper & paperboard. ^j HS codes 4702, 4703, 4802, 4804, 4810. ^k Sawnwood, veneer, industrial roundwood. ^l HS codes 4403, 4407, 4412. ^m Within HS 4403 and HS4407, tree species are specified by HS codes. Only the top-3 HS codes available for HS3304 (440349, 440399) and for HS4407 (440729, 440727, 440728) from the "value of imports from the source country by EU" were included. ⁿ Sawnwood, veneer, plywood. ^o HS codes 4407, 4412. ^p Within HS4407, tree species are specified by HS codes. Only the top-3 HS codes (440729, 440728, 440799) from the "value of imports from the source country by EU" were included.

5.1 Brazil-EU soy

Figure 1 presents a comprehensive mapping of the Brazil-EU soy value chain, from primary production in Brazil to its export to the EU. Soy production in Brazil has since the 1970s been notably expanded from the Southern states to the Central and Northern regions. Mato Grosso has been the largest soybean producing state in Brazil since 2000 (Bicudo Da Silva et al., 2020). Other main producing states include Rio Grande do Sul, Paraná, Goiás and Mato Grosso do Sul (IBGE, 2017). Recent years have also seen an expansion of soy cultivation into the agricultural frontiers of Maranhão, Tocantins, Piauí and Bahia (Russo Lopes et al., 2021). Soy producers may depend on financing or the supply of agricultural inputs, such as seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, and machines (Bicudo Da Silva et al., 2020). These inputs are predominantly provided by the “big four” agribusiness traders ADM, BUNGE, Cargill, and Dreyfus (I203; I205; Raucci et al., 2015).

Soybean production in Brazil is a highly industrialized sector dominated by large agribusiness producers and farm cooperatives. Small-scale soy businesses only exist in the South (e.g., in Rio Grande do Sul) (I203; I204). The first part of production includes the planting, managing and harvesting of soybeans. The second stage is characterized by either collecting and packaging the beans while keeping them as raw soybeans or processing them in a crushing plant into soy meal or oil (I205; Medina, 2022).

Traceability, however, remains a challenge. In the first and second stages, third-party dealers can be found indirectly providing soybeans from areas possibly prohibited under private and public initiatives, such as the Amazon Soy Moratorium, the Green Grain Protocol in Pará, and the Brazilian Forest Code (I204; Azevedo et al., 2015; Inakake de Souza et al., 2016). For instance, some deforestation-free farms can artificially increase their yield by adding at the end soybeans from farms that deforested land for their soybean production (I204). Furthermore, soybeans from a different country (e.g., Paraguay) can be mixed into a batch of soybeans supposedly only produced in Brazil (I205).

Consequently, informality and illegality partially persist across the soy value chain (I204; I205). Reacting to NGO and civil society pressure (I205), large international traders increasingly report on incorporating socio-economic and environmental sustainability standards in their annual corporate sustainability reports (e.g., BUNGE, 2023; Cargill, 2023) and are part of local deforestation-free initiatives such as the Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium (Gibbs et al., 2015). Nonetheless, traceability throughout the whole value chain in the vast territory of Brazil, including smaller producers and tracking in relation to deforested land and land tenure rights, remains a challenge (Medina & Thomé, 2021; Reis et al., 2023).

Brazil-EU27 SOY VALUE CHAIN

ECOLOGICAL CEILING (externalities): Deforestation, forest fires, biodiversity loss, etc.

Figure 1. Brazil-EU soy value chain map.

The third part of the value chain consists of distributing the soybeans and soy products domestically, exporting them to regional markets (e.g., Argentina), and internationally via ocean freight (e.g., China, and the EU), mostly by large traders, who are eminently present across the value chain. They purchase soybeans, transport them to their silos, and export them through ports (e.g., Port of Santarém) (I205). In 2021, Brazil was the second-largest global soy exporter, accounting for 14% of the total, of which 82% were raw soybeans, 16% soybean cake and 2% soybean oil (Reis & Moro, 2022).

China continues to be the largest importer of soy linked to deforestation and conversion from Brazil, reflecting an upward trend since 2013. In 2020, China's imports were linked to 229,000 ha of soy linked to deforestation, followed by 102,000 ha of Brazil's own domestic consumption. On the other hand, the EU's soy deforestation exposure in Brazil decreased. Compared to its 2015 peak at 201,000 ha, 2018 presented an exposure of 56,100 ha, which was reduced to 29,800 ha in 2020. This reflects an overall declining trend and shift in EU sourcing patterns favoring regions with less recent deforestation (Reis & Moro, 2022).

On the EU market, soy is imported through major ports, such as Rotterdam in the Netherlands, and then further distributed (I205). Portugal was the EU country of first import with the highest exposure to deforestation per ton of imported soy (Reis & Moro, 2022). Most soybeans undergo processing at crushing plants before retailers distribute them as finished products for final consumption. These mainly include animal feed for livestock and aquacultures, finalized food products, biofuel, and products for the chemical industry (e.g., industrial solvents) (I204; Heron et al., 2018).

Soy sector productive employment is male-dominated, especially with regards to land ownership and industrialized production processes (I204; I205). Women's involvement in the sector increases in international companies in sustainability and marketing roles. Furthermore, international companies like Cargill and BUNGE reported to employ around 21-34% of women in leadership roles (I204; BUNGE, 2023; Cargill, 2023). Cargill and ADM seek to achieve gender parity in leadership positions until 2030 (ADM, 2022; Cargill, 2023).

5.2 Brazil-EU timber

Figure 2 maps the Brazil-EU timber value chain. Key sourcing regions for native vegetation harvesting primarily include the Amazon biome. Timber is also harvested in the Cerrado and Atlantic Forest biomes. For planted forests, key sourcing regions are in the South (e.g., Paraná and Rio Grande do Sul). Forest management and harvesting in Brazil occur through forest concessions of public lands, in private lands (under the Brazilian Forest Code), and in community-based and association-based land (I202; De Souza et al., 2023).

Brazil-EU TIMBER VALUE CHAIN

ECOLOGICAL CEILING (externalities): Forest degradation, biodiversity loss, etc.

SOCIAL FOUNDATION (externalities): Human rights violations, gender equality, etc.

Figure 2. Brazil-EU timber value chain map.

Harvested timber is then either sold as roundwood or it undergoes further processing. Exported roundwood must originate from planted forests due to a ban on exporting native forest roundwood (I206). The key timber processing sites in Brazil are in the State of Pará, and key processed products include mouldings (softwood and hardwood), plywood, furniture, joinery, pulp and paper and sawnwood. A majority of Brazilian timber and timber products are sold domestically. Timber is also exported to the regional market, mostly as primary products, and to the EU (e.g., Belgium, Germany, France) and non-EU markets (e.g., USA, Mexico, China) (ATIBT, 2018; Edgar, 2022). Key exports from Brazil include pine and tropical sawnwood and plywood, as well as wooden furniture (ITTO, 2024). Downstream retailers and manufacturers sell, process and distribute timber and timber products on the EU market.

Brazil has a well-established legal policy framework with its Forest Code and timber supply chain documentation and traceability system called DOF+ (ATIBT, n.d.; Hoare, 2020; Ibama, 2024; Soares-Filho et al., 2014). The DOF+ traceability system is the tool for issuing, managing and monitoring the compulsory Document of Forest Origin license for transporting and storing forest products from Brazilian native species (Ibama, 2024). Nonetheless, informality and illegality are still a large part of the Brazilian timber market (Coelho-Junior et al., 2022; European Commission, 2020; Kleinschmit et al., 2021; Sotirov et al. 2022).

Similar to soy, the forest sector is also very male-dominated, with persisting gender inequality despite recent improvements (e.g., companies focus on including more women in leadership positions) (I208). Women are mostly involved in the upstream value chain in specific roles such as in nurseries, research and genetics, employed more in administrative and quality assurance roles. Only few women work in harvesting operations, transportation, and in leadership positions (I206; I208; Yoshioka et al., 2023).

5.3 Brazil-EU wood pulp

Figure 3 maps the Brazil-EU wood pulp value chain. In Brazil, the primary sources of wood for pulp production are pine and eucalyptus trees, comprising over 98% of the total volume. Additionally, pulp can be derived from alternative non-wood sources such as bamboo, babassu palm, sisal (agave), and agricultural residue like sugarcane bagasse. Brazil ranks as the fourth-largest producer of cellulose globally and holds the top position in eucalyptus pulp production worldwide (Ibá, 2018). The largest state producers of pine and eucalyptus trees are Minas Gerais, Mato Grosso do Sul, São Paulo, Paraná, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul (Edgar, 2022). Wood pulp mainly originates from trees planted in large plantations. Large businesses (e.g., Suzano, Eldorado, Klabin) and contractors dominate the wood pulp sector by managing the plantations, harvesting and transporting the wood, and processing it at wood chipping facilities and pulp mills. Small scale businesses are less common due to the high levels of investment needed for chipping and pulping technologies. Some small contractors are

involved in the less resource-intensive initial phase of forest management and planting trees (I208; Trase, 2017).

Large businesses and contractors directly chip the wood at facilities at plantation sites or ports, depending on the size of the production load and logistical setup. Chipped wood is then directly exported or processed further in Brazil through mechanical or chemical pulping. Some facilities additionally process wood production residues and waste for recycling or to generate energy. Finished wood pulp-based products include paper, paper-based products, textiles, biomass fuel, and specialty products such as food additives and chemicals (I208; Ibá, 2023; Suzano, 2023).

Brazil's wood pulp production, mainly from planted eucalyptus and pine fibers, totaled 21 million tons of wood pulp in 2020, making Brazil the second largest wood pulp producer worldwide. Besides distribution to the domestic market (around 26%), around 74% of wood pulp was exported. In 2020, Brazil exported 48% of its wood pulp to China, 15.8% to the USA, and 8.1% to Italy. Additional key EU importing countries include the Netherlands and Belgium (Trase, 2017). Export to other countries accounted for the remaining 28.1% (Edgar, 2022). In terms of paper and paperboard products, Brazil produced 10.2 million tons in 2020. With 80%, the majority was consumed on the domestic market; 20% was exported.

After import to the EU market, wood pulp undergoes mechanical or chemical processing. Imported wood pulp products and processed products are distributed and consumed on the EU market as finished products, including graphic papers, packaging material, and household/sanitary paper (UNECE & FAO, 2023).

Similar to the timber sector, informality and illegality are less part of the wood pulp value chain due to its vertical value chain, in which a few multinational companies tightly control their entire value chain (I208). Additionally, much wood pulp is certified (e.g., Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)) (I206; I208).

Brazil-EU WOOD PULP VALUE CHAIN

ECOLOGICAL CEILING (externalities): Deforestation, forest degradation, forest fires, biodiversity loss, etc.

Informal and illegal value chain activities

SOCIAL FOUNDATION (externalities): Human rights violations, gender equality, etc.

Figure 3. Brazil-EU wood pulp value-chain map.

Like in the timber sector, women mostly work in nurseries and research, being largely absent from technical and leadership positions (I208). Suzano employed 24.9% women in leadership positions in 2023 and Klabin 23.44% in 2022. Suzano and Klabin reported goals to increase gender inclusion to having 30% of women in leadership positions by 2030 (Suzano, 2023; Klabin, 2022). These gender inclusion goals are lower compared to the gender parity goals for leadership positions of multinational agribusiness companies like ADM and Cargill (see above). To mainstream gender inclusion in the forest sector, certification programs like FSC increasingly demand the inclusion of gender-based national indicators and components in audits (FSC, 2021; 2023). As example, under Principle 2.2 for Brazil, it is stated that the Organization should publicly declare its commitment to abolishing discriminatory practices and to promoting gender equality, and this commitment should be communicated to all workers (FSC, 2024).

5.4 Cameroon-EU timber

Figure 4 illustrates the flow of a general Cameroon-EU timber value chain, from left to right, including sawnwood, veneer, and logs as the main wooden products exported from Cameroon to the EU (Sustainable Timber Information Exchange, 2023). Formal forest management and exploitation mainly take place in forest concessions, council forests, sales of standing volume-permits in unclassified state forests, and community forests. Forest concessions and council forests are located in the Permanent Forest Domain (PFD) – comprising lands used solely for forestry and/or as wildlife habitat – and sales of standing volume -permits in unclassified state forests and community forests are located in the Non-Permanent Forest Domain (NPF) – comprising forestlands that may be used for other purposes than forestry (Republic of Cameroon, 1994).

In forest concessions and with sales of standing volume -permits, trees are felled, skidded to log landings, and transported further with trucks (Smith, 2006). Logging in community forests happens through the community itself or through contracts established with individuals and SMEs with, for instance, sales of standing volume -permits. In any case, logging must be done in an artisanal or semi-industrial way (e.g., in terms of equipment used; no logging roads but only footpaths to be used) (Cameroon Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife, 2009; Formété & Vermaat, 2001; Smith, 2006).

CAMEROON-EU27 TIMBER VALUE CHAIN (SAWNWOOD, VENEER & LOGS)

ECOLOGICAL CEILING (externalities): Deforestation, forest fires, biodiversity loss, etc.

SOCIAL FOUNDATION (externalities): Human rights violations, gender equality, etc.

Figure 4. Cameroon-EU timber value chain map.

In 2020, forest concessions produced around 1.8 million m³ of timber, council forests around 0.25 million m³, sales of standing volume -permits in unclassified state forests around 0.5 million m³, and community forests less than 0.1 million m³ (Cameroon Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife, 2020).

Post-logging, timber is moved through respective processing routes. At community forests, where processing is not done beyond sawing, the processing typically features portable sawmills next to felling, from where the sawnwood is moved to the roadside and taken with trucks to domestic markets or to export (Smith, 2006). Processing from other timber sources takes place at industrial scale sawmills and veneer mills. Logs are also exported in raw form.

Consequently, the products are distributed domestically, exported regionally, exported to non-EU, non-regional markets (from which some are re-exported to the EU after processing and/or manufacturing), or directly exported to EU markets. Community forests serve mainly domestic and regional export markets (Tsanga et al., 2022), while the other, mainly formal timber sources and processing routes feed all available markets. In the period 2014-2018, the EU was the most important trade partner of Cameroon in terms of the export value of wood products, followed by China and Vietnam (International Trade Centre, n.d.). Cameroon's timber exports to the EU consist mainly of sawnwood, while exports to Asia consist mostly of logs (International Trade Centre, n.d.). On the EU side, imports may undergo processing and/or manufacturing before retail and consumption.

Large forest concessionaires in Cameroon (> 100 employees) are export-oriented, particularly towards the EU-market (Hiolhiol, 2019). SMEs (≤ 100 employees), on the other hand, commonly target the local market and other export markets, such as those in Africa and Asia (Cameroon Ministry of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises, Social Economy and Handicrafts, n.d.; Hiolhiol, 2019).

Informal and illegal value chain activities can take place throughout the value chain. In Cameroon, informal exploitation (in PFD and NPFD) and sawmilling are related to a lack of a legal framework properly regulating these practices. Informal sawmilling comprised 57% of all (formal and informal) sawnwood production in 2009 (Lescuyer et al., 2013). 92% of this informal production was supplied to the domestic market, the rest was regionally exported (Lescuyer et al., 2013).

The timber sector in Cameroon is, generally speaking, male dominated. Timber companies do not normally have gender policies, with the exception of FSC-certified companies that are required to do so (FSC, 2020b, 2023). In the timber industry, the number of female workers tends to increase with higher wood processing stages (I212).

5.5 Gabon-EU timber

The Gabon-EU timber value chain (Figure 5) involves multiple stakeholders, including logging companies, sawmills, exporters, importers, manufacturers, retailers, and consumers. Sustainable forest management practices and adherence to transnational policies and (emergent) governance mechanisms (e.g., EUDR, FSC) help ensure the legality and/or sustainability of the timber trade between Gabon and the EU.

The Gabonese Forestry Code makes it compulsory to manage allocated forest concessions and to process timber. It also provides for four types of forestry permits: forest concessions under sustainable management, associated forestry permit, timber harvesting permits, and community forests (Madingou et al., 2019). In 2019, 51 Community Forests under a Definitive Agreement covered an area of 259,883 ha. There were 41 Community Forests under Provisional Agreement, covering 113,454 ha. In the same year, 97 forest concessions included 12,739,939 ha under forest management (Madingou et al., 2019).

In 2022, Gabon had 23.5 million ha of forest corresponding to 91% of the total land area (FAO, n.d.). These forests provide a diverse range of timber species, although logging focuses on some select species (e.g., Sapelli and Okoumé for the European market). The timber production phase involves logging activities, where trees are selectively harvested following sustainable forestry practices to ensure the long-term viability of the forests (Bayol et al., 2012). Once harvested, the logs are transported to sawmills or processing facilities within Gabon. Here, they undergo various processes, such as sawing, drying, and treatment to convert them into usable timber products like planks, boards, or veneers. The processed timber is then graded based on quality standards (FRMi, 2018).

After processing, the timber products are distributed in the domestic market and exported from Gabon to other markets, including the EU. This involves packaging and shipping the products via sea or air freight (Lescuyer & Cerutti, 2013). China and the EU, followed by India, have been the leading destinations for timber products from Gabon in terms of exported value during 2017-2021; whereby the role of China is dominant in sawnwood and the EU leads in veneer and plywood (International Trade Centre, n.d.).

Upon arrival in the EU, the imported timber products go through customs clearance procedures. After, the timber products are distributed within the EU countries through wholesalers or directly supplied to manufacturers who use them for various purposes, such as construction or furniture production. In this phase of the value chain, manufacturers transform the imported timber into finished products like furniture items or construction materials. These finished products are then sold in retail stores and used for domestic consumption within EU countries.

GABON-EU27 TIMBER VALUE CHAIN (SAWNWOOD, VENEER & PLYWOOD)

ECOLOGICAL CEILING (externalities): Deforestation, forest fires, biodiversity loss, etc.

Figure 5. Gabon-EU timber value chain map.

Throughout the value chain, waste materials generated during timber processing or manufacturing are managed and recycled where possible. This includes reusing sawdust for energy production or recycling wood scraps into composite materials (Bikoro Bi, 2020).

Compared to other countries with a large forest mass, where logging is struggling to make a significant contribution to the country's economy, the turnover of the timber industry in Gabon rose from 184 billion FCFA to 704 billion FCFA (+282%) between 2014 and 2022. The value of processed wood exports reached 610 billion FCFA in 2021, creating more than 6000 additional jobs since 2010. In the meantime, Gabon has become Africa's leading producer of plywood and the world's sixth largest, thanks to the 100% processing of logs in the country (Bayol et al., 2022).

However, logging in Gabon has been criticized for its lack of transparency and unsustainable practices. Reports have revealed cases of corruption, illegal allocation of forest concessions and excessive exploitation of resources (Worah et al., 2019). The Gabonese government has taken steps to regulate logging and promote sustainable resource management (African Development Bank, 2019). In 2002, it adopted the Forest Code that sets out rules for the allocation of concessions, the protection of protected areas and the sustainable management of forests. Gabon has also embarked on a forest certification process to improve the traceability of extracted timber and guarantee its legality and sustainability.

Much like in Cameroon, the Gabonese timber sector is male dominated. FSC-certified companies, which are required to develop and adopt gender policies as per FSC requirements (FSC, 2020a), are a minority in the timber sector. Although not necessarily representative of the sector as a whole, one Gabonese timber company had 10% of its employees and 11% of its management female in 2022 (Compagnie des Bois du Gabon, 2022).

PART II – VALUE CHAIN ACTORS’ BEHAVIORAL RESPONSES

Part II consists of three sections. First, we outline our theoretical framework of drivers of behavioral responses to policies and governance mechanisms. Second, we introduce the methods used in the empirical research conducted. Third, we present the results.

6 PART II THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Drawing on literature related to regulations and compliance, institutionalism, and behavioral responses (e.g., McKay, 2001; Ramcilovic-Suominen & Epstein, 2012; Scott, 2013; Williamson & Lynch-Wood, 2021; Köthke and Sotirov, 2024), we distinguish between behavioral drivers (namely regulative, normative, economic, and cultural-cognitive logics) and actors' behavioral responses (Figure 6). The behavioral drivers are rooted in grand social change theories like institutionalism (linked to regulative logic), sociology and constructivism (linked to normative logic), political economy (linked to economic logic), and social psychology (linked to cultural-cognitive logic) (Sotirov et al., 2020; Köthke and Sotirov, 2024). The four drivers can be understood as broad logics that respond to different sources or types of stimuli, motivating actors to adopt specific behaviors.

Figure 6. Theoretical framework of behavioral drivers and responses.

The regulative logic posits that formal rules, insofar as they carry penalties for non-compliance and/or rewards for compliance, influence actors' behavior, as the actors are expected to seek to maximize benefits or minimize costs for themselves (Becker, 1968). Thus, a key consideration is how actors perceive the associated costs and benefits of complying versus not complying. In this context, law enforcement (e.g., financial penalties or confiscation of goods) can have an important deterrence effect. This also relates to the broader governance context (e.g., enforcement capacities of the public sector, presence of corruption), which can strengthen or weaken the influence of the regulative logic (Köthke and Sotirov, 2024).

The normative logic refers to actor-external norms (e.g., zero deforestation), for instance from peers, NGOs, media, or society in general, that determine appropriate ways of behaving (Cialdini & Trost, 1998; Scott, 2013). In this sense, actors can be concerned about how their behavior is perceived by others, affecting their reputation. Furthermore, following or supporting norms (or not) can lead to social approval (or disapproval) (Helferich et al., 2023). Thus, even when normative pressures are not codified in hard laws (when they become rules), they can have an influence on actors' behavior. Moreover, the normative logic asserts that acceptance of a pressure influences actors' behavioral responses. Acceptance relates to actors' willingness, desire, or perceived legitimacy to meet the requirements of a pressure (Ramcilovic-Suominen & Epstein, 2012; Williamson & Lynch-Wood, 2021). Legitimacy reflects influences emerging from the political environment, referring to the consent of actors and their willingness to accept a pressure or its source (Oliver, 1991; Ramcilovic-Suominen & Epstein, 2012). A pressure that is perceived as legitimate by actors is more accepted by them, thus being more likely to induce behavior as intended by the pressure.

The economic logic suggests that markets and market conditions influence actors' behavior by creating market incentives (e.g., eased market access, price premiums) that actors seek to benefit from, and disincentives (e.g., restricted market access, low profitability) that they aim to avoid (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012; Sotirov et al., 2020; Köthke and Sotirov, 2024). For example, market access costs and benefits and the associated market access requirements that a market imposes could influence actors' adopted behavior (e.g., compliance or withdrawal from a market). Macroeconomic conditions and trends, geopolitics, wars, and pandemics, for example, can also reflect in the economic logic (Ramcilovic-Suominen & Epstein, 2012; Sabatier, 1988). For example, a crisis situation could influence the demand of a commodity, which could influence its going market price. Also, the availability of resources (e.g., financial) by actors to respond to pressures can drive their potential responses (May & Wood, 2003; Williamson & Lynch-Wood, 2021). For instance, a small organization could have relatively limited resources and ability to respond to a pressure.

The cultural-cognitive logic assumes that legal subjects' internal, moral obligations that they hold affect their behavior (Sutinen & Kuperan, 1999). Following this logic, actors behave based on perceptions of what is "the right thing to do", irrespective of what other actors hold of it. Such perspectives can be reflected in policies of organizations representing their organizational values, for instance. The cultural-cognitive logic is also linked to actors' knowledge in that whether actors are aware of and knowledgeable about a pressure influences their responses to it (Williamson & Lynch-Wood, 2021; Köthke and Sotirov, 2024). For example, lack of awareness or a low level of knowledge could hinder (informed) behavioral responses, thus weakening the influence of the cultural-cognitive logic.

Concerning behavioral responses, they are the ways in which actors react to institutional pressures, such as policies and governance mechanisms, arising from the environment (Oliver, 1991). Behavioral responses can be consciously planned and strategic, or unplanned and passive (Oliver, 1991; Eberlein et al., 2014; Marques & Eberlein, 2021;). Furthermore, they can be dynamic and vary over time (McKay, 2001; Cashore et al., 2021), rather than be observed as a “one-shot static occurrence” (Pramudya et al., 2018, p. 2). The timing of the responses can be anticipatory (in anticipation of a pressure), present (ongoing), or long-term (intend to pursue in the future).

7 PART II METHODS

7.1 Data collection

Our data collection consisted of semi-structured qualitative interviews. First, we identified key informant interviewees following nonprobability sampling; specifically, we combined purposive and snowball sampling (Neuman, 2014). Through purposive sampling, we ensured that key actors involved in or knowledgeable about the five focal value chains, including their different stages (from supply side to demand side), were covered. To capture a plurality of views and triangulate research findings (Neuman, 2014), the array of actors interviewed included public actors, international organizations, NGOs, research/training institutions, think tanks, consultants, certification, finance, businesses, and business associations/federations. Through snowball sampling, we identified additional key actors. Our final sample size was informed by reaching the saturation point where no new significant insights any longer emerged during the data collection (Neuman, 2014).

Second, we developed a semi-structured interview guide based on key theory-derived analytical categories (Supplementary Material 2). The data collection method of key informant interviews was deemed appropriate and justified, as our objective was to gather interviewees' subjective views and perspectives on the topic (Flick, 2018).

Third, we obtained written informed consent from the interviewees (Flick, 2018). Where interview partners did not consent to the interview being recorded, we took detailed notes. Interviews were conducted in English, German, Portuguese and French, depending on the interviewee's preference. 93 interviewees were interviewed in-person in Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon, Belgium, and Germany, and 107 were interviewed online, depending on the interviewee's availability and preference. In total, we interviewed 200 interviewees from October 2023 to April 2024 (Supplementary Material 1). Table 2 shows an overview of these interviewees.

Table 2. Overview of interviewees with the interviews focused on the preparation for the EUDR implementation. The country/region indicates the value chain region that the interview was topically focused on.

	Public actor	Public-private partnership	International organization	NGO	Research/training organization, think tank & consultant	Certification	Finance	Business	Business association/federation	All
Brazil	16	2	5	12	13	4	3	6	9	70
Cameroon	6	0	0	10	9	2	0	11	2	40
Gabon	4	2	0	7	5	3	2	5	5	33
EU & other	13	0	5	7	7	7	0	10	8	57
All	39	4	10	36	34	16	5	32	24	200

7.2 Data analysis

A qualitative content analysis of the key informant interviews was carried out. Firstly, we transcribed the interview recordings and anonymized them. We assigned a unique ID to every interviewee (e.g., "I-n"), recording also their geographic location (e.g., Europe-based, Gabon-based), the topical focus of the interview (e.g., Brazil-focused, Cameroon-focused), and their actor type (e.g., NGO, business) (Supplementary Material 1). This anonymous interviewee ID is used when referencing analyzed data in the results. Further, all direct quotes from interviews not conducted in English were translated by the authors.

Next, applying thematic analysis, we coded the interviews using MAXQDA qualitative analysis software. The coding was performed by four researchers, and we aimed to ensure intercoding reliability and consistency in two ways. Firstly, we adopted deductive coding, meaning that our joint thematic coding scheme was built on the theory-founded interview guide (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This harmonized coding scheme was jointly developed by the researchers (as were the foundational theoretical framework and interview guide), providing guidance and definitions to the individual codes. The codes captured aspects of actors' behavioral drivers and responses to the EUDR. Secondly, we adopted a harmonized and aligned approach to the coding through frequent discussions and exchange during the coding process. We also held an in-person workshop in June 2024 to share and discuss preliminary findings among the combined research team, which informed the ongoing coding process.

We qualitatively assessed the relative importance of the four behavioral logics based on the influence ascribed to them by the interviewees. Hence, our analysis was sensitive to the interviewees' statements in describing the four logics as influencing (or not) business actors' behavioral responses to the EUDR. We focus on examining the behavioral responses of businesses (producers, traders, processors, manufacturers, and retailers) as the key regulated actor under the EUDR. Although EU-external business actors are not directly regulated under the EUDR, our analysis includes them, since they can still be indirectly affected. We also assess the behavioral responses of business associations, because they can have important agency in influencing implementation for businesses. Our findings also introduce the role of other actors (e.g., public actors, NGOs) in relation to business actors and EUDR implementation. As for timing of the responses, our analytical focus lies on preparation for the EUDR implementation, with the underlying assumption that although the new EUDR rules start applying to businesses from 30 December 2025 onwards (or 30 June 2026 for micro and small enterprises), businesses (can) begin preparing for implementation before that.

It is relevant to note that because the EUDR was not yet implemented during the study's data collection, interviewees' stated behavioral responses may not fully

reflect what they *de facto* intend to do. As such, more of our analytical focus lies on behavioral drivers supported by the theoretical framework of the four logics.

8 PART II RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the interview analysis. The findings are structured according to the value chain regions (Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon, and EU), separating between behavioral responses and drivers. Table 3 summarizes the behavioral logics and responses by different value chain business actors.

Table 3. Summary overview of the behavioral logics and responses by different value chain business actors.

Value chain business actors	Behavioral logics	Key behavioral responses
Business associations	-	-Information dissemination -Technical compliance support to member companies
Supply side		
Small producers/processors/manufacturers	Regulative: limited to no influence (e.g., EUDR hard rules not directly applicable on the supply side)	-Abandon EU market, divert to other markets -Partnership with larger businesses to maintain EU market access
	Normative: less influential on small market actors (e.g., no direct normative pressure by consumers)	
	Economic: strong influence (e.g., limited capacity to produce EUDR-compliant products)	
	Cultural-cognitive: limited to no influence (e.g., intrinsic motivations often rank low)	
Large producers/processors/manufacturers	Regulative: limited to no influence (e.g., EUDR hard rules not directly applicable on the supply side)	-Ensure products are compliant with the EUDR -Simplify value chain (e.g., removal of small market actors) -Segregation of EUDR-compliant supply
	Normative: relatively strong influence (e.g., reputation protection by brands)	
	Economic: strong influence (e.g., want to maintain access to lucrative EU market)	
	Cultural-cognitive: varying influence (e.g., organizational values of some)	
Demand side		
Small producers/processors/manufacturers	Regulative: strong influence (e.g., avoid penalties)	-Ensure compliance -Some may be lax and gamble on not getting controlled at import -Some "operators" to become "traders" (as per EUDR terminology)
	Normative: relatively strong influence (e.g., reputation protection for peers)	
	Economic: strong influence (e.g., ensure continued resource availability)	
	Cultural-cognitive: varying influence (e.g., organizational values of some)	
Large producers/processors/	Regulative: strong influence (e.g., avoid penalties)	-Ensure compliance -Simplify value chain (e.g., removal of intermediaries)

manufacturers	Normative: relatively strong influence (e.g., reputation protection by brands)	
	Economic: strong influence (e.g., market will punish for non-compliance)	
	Cultural-cognitive: varying influence (e.g., organizational values of some)	

8.1 Brazil

Behavioral drivers

Businesses from the three sectors in Brazil affirmed that the main behavioral driver for compliance follows an economic logic (e.g., I174; I175; I200). Illustrated by the following quote from a large business from the agricultural sector: "We are just doing it to avoid losing the market and we are not going to stop selling. (I171)" No interviewee rejected the fact that economics plays a role in whether businesses comply or not. Since these sectors actually have other larger buyers (domestically for timber and wood pulp and China for soy), the driver to comply relies on the company's relationship with or dependency on the EU market, as illustrated by this agricultural sector business association representative: "It's purely economic, we want to comply not to lose the EU market, which continues to be important. (I198)" Furthermore, especially for the timber and wood pulp sectors, they see the EU market as one that gives more value, and pays more, for certain products, so they will not leave the market (I154; I161).

Interviewees then noted how the regulative logic follows the economic logic, meaning that only once a business decides to comply based on its economic interest of selling to the EU, will it then make sure to produce compliant products for regulatory reasons, not to be penalized (e.g., I165; I185; I192). A research organization representative who has been studying the process stated: "But of course the economy is reinforced by the threat of punishment, and Europe doesn't play around with these things. [Businesses] are realizing this and don't want to be punished. (I163)" It must be said that this perception may also be a misunderstanding since direct penalties and punishments will only be incurred on EU operators/traders, not non-EU ones. An agricultural certification scheme representative added that soy traders with an EU presence perceive potential EUDR penalties as high, so they would not risk non-compliance (I158). A timber business representative also stated that certain changes only happen when there are regulations and rules, as it puts pressure on businesses (I188). Representatives from an agricultural business association and a research organization also acknowledged that the regulative logic is probably more prominent for EU businesses, since for them it is not a choice (I142; I168). Therefore, there is a clear distinction between the importance of the regulative logic on EU and non-EU businesses, the latter giving higher importance to the economic logic, since producing compliant products would depend on their EU market share.

The normative logic appeared with less relevance. When mentioned as an affirmative logic behind businesses' behavioral responses, it was usually in combination with the economic and regulative logics (e.g., I142; I184; I189). An international NGO representative described it as the logic that comes before the creation of regulations (I153), since, as a state actor also emphasized, "the government makes laws to ensure what society wants" (I187). Other non-business actors stated that the normative logic can appear, especially for larger companies, to protect their image in relation to shareholders and consumers (e.g., I137; I158; I174). Two agricultural business actors rejected this logic by saying that consumers do not actually care about this (I168; I171), and NGO actors and a business association added that large businesses do not feel threatened anymore by these reputational issues and that NGOs have lost their normative power (I145; I146; I166).

Finally, minor relevance was given to the cultural-cognitive logic, only with reference to certain businesses which already held ambitious sustainable and deforestation-free commitments before the EUDR (e.g., I133; I142; I191). On the other hand, certain non-business actors (e.g., NGO, state actors) rejected this logic, mentioning that businesses do not truly have this intrinsic value, and if it is stated in their values it is because it came after other logics, either from an economic interest (e.g., not to lose market), from a regulative framework (e.g., public policy), or normative logic (i.e., pressures by others) (e.g., I164; I189; I196).

In general, we did not observe large differences in the stated influence of behavioral drivers across sectors. However, for the soy and wood pulp sectors, being highly vertical and globally integrated and, thus, more dependent on their EU counterparts, the regulative logic appeared more prominently in their statements in comparison to the timber sector.

Behavioral responses

Based on all interviewees' responses, the general behavior of businesses in the soy, timber and wood pulp sectors in Brazil are of understanding how they can produce compliant products using their existing systems (e.g., traceability, forest monitoring) they have in place, but waiting on additional guidance and practical information on EUDR implementation, to be published by the European Commission. Open questions related to the EUDR country benchmarking system to be conducted (e.g. the method for categorizing high risk countries/regions), the EUDR information system in which EU operators/traders will have to submit their due diligence statements, and how to provide geolocation information for each product (e.g., I163; I167; I189). Many of these open questions are being answered by the European Commission's frequently asked questions (FAQ) document, with the intention to have it regularly updated (European Commission, 2024a). An example from the wood pulp sector and certain timber companies is that they claim that given the nature of their certified planted forests, deforestation has not happened for years now, so they will have to spend

a lot of unnecessary time and money to prove compliance, which will not change much in what they already do in practice (e.g., I136; I154; I161). Moreover, a misperception or misinformation among these interviewees was observed, since many seem to be convinced that the further due diligence requirements and proving geolocation information will only be the case if Brazil is considered a high-risk country. If EU operators source from a high-risk country one would expect them to ask more questions around legality and deforestation-free, so high-risk country suppliers may get asked to provide copies of more paperwork. The only actual difference between high and standard-risk countries is that there will be more EUDR compliance checks on EU businesses who import from high-risk countries, and a greater proportion of the goods will be checked. The EUDR legal text states that operators should be allowed to exercise simplified due diligence for relevant products from low-risk countries or parts thereof. Thus, due diligence will always be exercised.

Businesses from all sectors stated they did not disagree with the objective of combating deforestation, but rather with the form it is required in (e.g., I131; I151; I154), with the fear that it will be more of a bureaucratic exercise of filling in forms and ticking boxes, rather than actually making an environmental difference (I132; I142; I195). A representative of an agricultural sector business association shared this concern regarding the form in which compliance is demanded: "Unfortunately, the European culture is to impose and not want to pay anything, and this creates a lot of friction...The demand of the European consumer is legitimate, but [then] they don't engage. You identify the problem, [but] don't help. That's [...] not fair. (I166)"

Businesses from the wood pulp sector also shared discontent over the time and energy spent and increased costs in only trying to figure out the 'gaps' in their systems, and thus, what needs to be additionally done (I154; I175). It was stated that they would need a delay of at least six months of the EUDR's entry into application to transition and produce compliant products (I169; I195).

Business associations in all sectors have embraced the role of gathering information, finding alignment among businesses, working with other sectors to exchange learnings, and with the government to assist in a possible national traceability system (e.g., I151; I180; I194). Smaller businesses reported waiting on larger ones to understand what will be needed for products to be compliant, yet also fearing being left behind due to their lower capabilities to adapt at a faster pace (e.g., I145; I172; I190). An agricultural business representative and an NGO representative also mentioned that larger businesses have a market advantage by being able to produce compliant products faster and will use this as a market opportunity (I153; I157).

Businesses and non-business actors (e.g., international organization, certification) stated that businesses' responses today feed on learnings from other past

experiences (i.e., the timber and wood pulp sectors from the European Union timber regulation (EUTR) and the soy sector from genetically modified organism requirements) (e.g., I140; I161; I169). Despite their familiarity with the EUTR and being confident that the Brazilian timber legality system (DOF+) and FSC standards should provide a good benchmark for compliance, the timber and wood pulp sectors have understood that there will be extra work to provide the plot of land information for each product, as well as provide additional information to help EU operators perform their due diligence obligations (e.g., I161; I180; I188). The timber and wood pulp sectors differed in two main concerns: the timber businesses seemed to be concerned as to what kind of documentation will be needed to prove compliance with the social and human rights requirements (I161; I162), and the wood pulp sector is highly concerned with the traceability to the plot of land, since products such as a paper or a book could have thousands of polygons to report on. They mentioned that they can be certain that the timber they use is deforestation-free, but as it is processed, it is all mixed together, making it difficult to trace exact polygons for each product (I169; I195). This concern stems from a misunderstanding, since “overdeclaration” of geolocations has been informed possible by the European Commission. It is known that deforestation-free products from different origins will be mixed as you progress along the value chain, and this list of possible geolocations from which a product might originate will simply get longer. “Overdeclaration” of geolocations is not forbidden, it would just increase the number of plots for which an EU operator must prove the deforestation-free status (European Commission, 2024b).

Another concern of the wood pulp sector is related to data security, since their products have a large global value chain, and a lot of company and market related information would be shared in the requested system (I169; I170; I195). A business representative illustrated this concern: “It’s a question of confidentiality and data security, not only with the EU itself, but also when triangulating information, because I’m having to provide the information to a third party, who is also subject to [this] law...I don’t know how they’re going to use this information...and then they’re going to come and charge me with something for the inaccuracy of the information they’re using incorrectly. (I195)” These genuine concerns, however, may be misconceptions of the EUDR, since the EU’s Information System only requires geolocations, not additional details on producer names or addresses. Company or national traceability systems might require additional information, and producers may have concerns how this is used or shared, but this is not specifically due to EUDR compliance (European Commission, 2024b).

For the soy sector, there is a more prominent behavior difference between the large trader companies and certain smaller rural producers, which is also reflected by the role of representing business associations (i.e., ABIOVE and

APROSOJA). Larger trader companies (e.g., BUNGE, CARGILL, AMAGGI), represented by ABIOVE, have consolidated traceability systems and their own deforestation-free commitments, and are also signatories of the Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM). They have a larger overview of the sector in the country and can logistically shift their production and exports "corridor", depending on the demand (e.g., I157; I166; I171). Their main work has been in finding out how to provide fully deforestation-free segregated soybeans from the land, to the silos, to the port, and shipping, since businesses work with a lot of shared renting of spaces and logistics (e.g., I164; I168; I190). Certain smaller rural producers, represented by APROSOJA, who are against the Amazon Soy Moratorium, are also openly against the EUDR for the same reason that it demands compliance beyond national legislation (i.e., Brazil's Forest Code). These mainly express discontentment and that they do not need the European market and can sell to others, such as China (e.g., I140; I177; I194).

Finally, interviewees representing businesses and non-business actors (e.g., research and international organizations) from these three sectors stated that those who rely on the European market will find a way of complying, and those who do not will wait and see what happens, selling to other markets (domestic or other export markets) instead (e.g., I155; I157; I176). Thus, there was a common understanding among the different actors that what will simply happen are big operational differences between producers who export to the EU and those who do not, reflecting different standards, but not necessarily solving the problem of deforestation, as there is much space in Brazil for market and geographical leakage (e.g., I150; I191; I200).

8.2 Cameroon

Behavioral drivers

For timber businesses in Cameroon exporting to the EU, the economic logic is key, as mainly economic factors were described by both business and non-business interviewees as the driver for producing EUDR compliant products (e.g., I2; I21; I40). Accordingly, the EU is perceived as the most lucrative market for wood products and this high profitability drives the businesses' aspiration to continue exporting there. This was illustrated by a research organization representative: "We know that the European market is one of the biggest in the world, and it also has very sensitive niche markets [that] pay a lot if you manage to meet all the conditions, you're sure to sell your products at a very good price. So there's already this economic interest. (I4)" Furthermore, business and non-business interviewees argued that to the extent that the businesses need to implement changes in their operation in order to meet the EUDR requirements, they are willing to do so, as long as it makes sense in terms of profitability (e.g., I2; I22; I35). Moreover, as argued by business and technical service provider representatives, businesses need to conform to the demands of the EU market if they wish to sell there, that is, they may need to provide the necessary documentation requested by EU operators to inform their due diligence processes as part of business

transactions with them (I16; I29; I30). Similarly, a Vietnam-based representative from an NGO also commented that for Vietnamese forest sector businesses, the EU is a key market, which motivates their intent and willingness to produce products compliant with the EUDR (I92).

Conversely, if business profitability takes a hit due to EUDR compliance, it could trigger shifts in exports from EU to elsewhere, as an NGO representative noted: “The margins in the logging sector are quite high still. They will say no, but... they are high. So they can afford losing part of the margin by selling to Asia. (I14)” Similarly, those businesses that primarily target non-EU markets (e.g., in Asia) will continue to do so and adopt an attitude of indifference towards the EUDR for economic reasons, as argued by the same NGO representative: “If I’m a businessman, I’ll be looking at the options. Can I make more money by taking timber from almost any place and selling it in the market offering a lower price than Europe but still making good profit? If the answer is yes, why should I not do it? (I14)” An NGO representative further cautioned that an observed lack of positive incentives by the EUDR could have an overall negative effect on forest biodiversity in the country: “If there are incentives, policy incentives, market incentives, ecosystem incentives, it can really help a company implement [the EUDR]. Otherwise, and that has always been my fear, the EUDR might be more detrimental to the tropical forest than the intent of it. Because there’s no incentive. Then everybody will give up their business and the Chinese will come in. [...] So in terms of sustainability, I believe that the EUDR poses more risks than brings solutions to the tropical timber sector, taking the case of Cameroon and the Congo Basin in particular. (I6)”

After the economic logic, interviewees ascribed minor relevance to the normative logic as a behavioral driver. Businesses will want to comply with the EUDR in order to have “an image abroad of an organization that works in compliance with the laws and regulations in force relating to environmental protection, worker protection and so on”, protecting their business reputation, as noted by a forest sector business representative (I28). Apart from that, a forest sector business representative acknowledged also NGO pressure as influencing business behavior (I36), although NGO representatives did not find this relevant (I1, I6). An NGO representative said: “NGO campaigns in Cameroon in particular and in Congo Basin have been, for the last 10 years, reducing. [...] It’s because most of the companies used to sell their timber to Europe [but don’t do so anymore]. The public opinion in Europe is very aware of the environmental issues. But if you cannot hit the companies’ pockets, there’s nothing you can do. [...] The government is also not strong enough, or the governance aspect of the country. And that’s a key thing also. In a country where the government cares about enforcing its law, it can make a difference. Otherwise, I find it quite difficult. (I6)”

The regulative and cultural-cognitive logics had comparatively weak influence, overall, according to the interviewees. For the regulative logic, this is so because

the hard rules that it imposes on businesses directly affect only businesses operating and trading in the EU market and not those that are based in Cameroon (I18). Moreover, law enforcement – and forest governance in general – in Cameroon was understood as weak, which includes the problem of corruption, as described by public sector and technical service provider representatives (I1, I6). This could even facilitate non-compliance behavior with the EUDR, as exemplified by a research organization representative (I15) about businesses' thinking: "I have money, I pass on my wood and I am able to pass on my illegal wood to legal wood, from uncertified wood to certified wood." Concerning the cultural-cognitive logic, non-business interviewees argued that knowledge of the EUDR among businesses in Cameroon is still low, hindering proper responses to it (e.g., I7; I8; I23). In addition, interviewees gave the cultural-cognitive logic low but mixed importance when it comes to organizational values. For example, an NGO representative noted: "It has to be said that very few operators are concerned with preserving the forest. (I13)"

Behavioral responses

Both business and non-business interviewees described the timber sector businesses in Cameroon to be mostly ready and prepared for the EUDR, with no significant changes foreseen as needed in their operation compared to the pre-existing EUTR (e.g., I5; I10; I16). This concerns particularly businesses that are already linked to exports to the EU, which are mainly businesses larger in size and often certified against a voluntary sustainability certification (e.g., FSC) or legality verification (e.g., Origine et Légalité des Bois) scheme, or both. Business and non-business interviewees said that these businesses were studying and assessing the EUDR and what it means for them (e.g., I5; I24; I28). In connection, representatives of NGOs and forest sector business associations reported that the associations had had meetings with the EU on the needs of the sector in relation to the EUDR, communicating them onwards to their member businesses (I12; I17). Broadly, interviewees believed that producing products compliant with the EUDR will mainly be a matter of communicating a larger part of already collected and existing information to the EU buyers, as put by a forest sector business representative: "Maybe this regulation [...] adds a few more elements in the documents to be provided, because if it's in terms of procedures, there's almost nothing new. (I32)" Traceability to the plot, for example, already exists as part of a national timber traceability system (SIGIF-2) or the above-mentioned voluntary tools (e.g., I9; I30; I38). However, non-business interviewees observed that in the context of the EU-Cameroon Voluntary Partnership Agreement, the EU did not consider SIGIF-2 to be reliable and that Cameroon would first need to convince the EU of its appropriateness for the EUDR (e.g., I9; I13; I20). Both business and non-business interviewees cast some doubts over the EUDR requirements related to compliance with anti-corruption laws, human rights under international law, and not causing forest degradation, as it was unclear how or what kind of evidence could or should be provided in these respects (e.g., I28; I36; I40). Over the longer term, businesses expected to hire more staff and increase

communication and exchange with the EU buyers as part of EUDR compliance (e.g., I24; I35; I36).

Some SME and non-certified businesses also export to the EU market, and these could face comparatively higher costs in achieving production of EUDR compliant products. Sometimes, they might even lack the capacity altogether for ensuring producing products compliant with the EUDR, as argued by representatives from NGOs and technical service providers (I6; I16; I18). Hence, non-business interviewees expected SME and non-certified businesses to wholly abandon the EU market and shift their sales to other markets (e.g., I13; I14; I18). In relation to this, an NGO representative cautioned that community forests would be precluded from accessing the EU market because of the EUDR: "The small players will definitely be out of the [EU] market. I don't see any small artisanal logger or community forest going into this system. That's just impossible. So the EUDR might contribute to the economic marginalization of the local communities who are interested in the timber business. (I6)" It must also be noted that a majority of timber products from Cameroon are sold to non-EU markets, such as China and Vietnam (International Trade Centre, n.d.). According to a public sector representative, businesses in Cameroon that are exporting to these markets are indifferent toward the EUDR as they see no implications from it (I10). However, public sector and business representatives alike raised the possibility that the EUDR could induce such Asian businesses sourcing from Cameroon to start conducting EUDR-equivalent due diligence on their Cameroonian suppliers, if they use these wood materials to manufacture products that are eventually exported to the EU (I10; I24). Similarly, a Vietnam-based representative from an NGO, speaking about forest sector businesses in Vietnam that are involved in global imports (including from the Congo Basin) and exports (including to the EU), claimed that they will start requesting more information from their overseas suppliers to ensure the EUDR compliance of their EU-bound exports (I92).

8.3 Gabon

Behavioral drivers

The economic logic explains the behavior of both businesses that seek the EU market (and producing EUDR compliant products) and those that do not. First, business and non-business interviewees pointed out the economic logic as the key logic motivating (certain) businesses to maintain or seek EU market access and compliance with the EUDR (e.g., I41; I50; I58). As per business and business actor representatives, this relates to the perceived high profitability of the EU market and that it remunerates for legality and sustainability efforts, such as voluntary certification, that businesses may undergo (e.g., I41; I51; I62). Thus, timber businesses in Gabon currently engaged in the EU market would want to continue their engagement even with the EUDR. Additionally, EU buyer pressure was mentioned as motivating the producing of EUDR compliant products (I66). Forest sector business association and NGO representatives also claimed that buyers of Gabonese timber in Asia will start exerting pressure (e.g., for obtaining

sustainability certification) on Gabonese suppliers when these Asian businesses target the EU market with their transformed wood products (I49; I69). However, a research organization representative argued that non-EU buyers would be unlikely to put such pressure on their Gabonese suppliers (I48). Non-business interviewees also raised that further positive economic incentives from the EU side (e.g., technical compliance support, positive price signals) would be needed and would motivate additional companies to seek EU market access (e.g., I47; I59; I64). Moreover, a consultancy representative explained that positive economic incentives in the supply side are important for motivating EUDR compliant best practices, taking the example of the Gabonese legal framework, according to which forest concessionaires that are sustainability certified pay just half the amount of the hectare-based area fee on their concessions compared to non-certified forest concessionaires (I50).

Second, business and non-business interviewees also highlighted the economic logic as a key explanation for why – still – most businesses in Gabon do not seek EU market access (e.g., I44; I46; I59). The specific aspects raised here were that the Asian market remains the most important market destination for most timber businesses in Gabon (particularly for non-certified businesses), that the EUDR only adds disincentives, and that the EU market is difficult to access with requirements that are too constraining. Furthermore, a representative of the forest sector business association, representing Asian-owned businesses in Gabon, explained that demanding product requirements in the EU market – as compared to the Asian market – lead to lower profitability: “In fact, it's not interesting to sell to the European market, for me it's not interesting at all. Because the Chinese market isn't demanding in terms of quality [...], even small portions of 30-40 cm in length, I can find a market for that. It's true that the price is low, but we don't waste the wood product. Everything is used, whereas the European market is complicated because it requires fixed dimensions. [...] There's too much waste for us. I'd rather sell at a lower price, but I can export [everything]. (I66)”

Interviewees described the normative logic also playing a role in EUDR compliance, albeit a minor one. A finance sector representative noted brand image and reputation of businesses as relevant, as complying with the EUDR can enhance the trust and attractiveness of these businesses in Gabon (I67). Furthermore, a research organization representative acknowledged the role of media and NGO pressure but also found it insufficient for influencing business behavior (I48).

Interviewees described the regulative and cultural-cognitive logics having overall a weak influence. A forest sector business association representative argued that it is the regulative logic that would motivate companies to act, but that there is no such pressure from the EUDR on businesses in Gabon (I49). A forest sector business representative described an expectation that China will adopt an EUDR-like regulation, or a regulation that will demand legality, and this will motivate companies in Gabon to adjust their practices (I54). Concerning the

cultural-cognitive logic, an NGO representative observed that the EUDR as a new policy development was still relatively poorly understood in Gabon (I69). Regarding organizational values, a forest sector business representative pointed out their corporate social responsibility policy as being aligned with and motivating sales to the EU market (I41).

Behavioral responses

In Gabon, business and non-business interviewees noted that most timber businesses that have major exports to the EU – forming a minority of the overall sector – have European ownership and possess a certificate of sustainability and/or legality from a voluntary scheme (e.g., FSC) (e.g., I42; I44; I46). These businesses felt prepared for the EUDR already with their current practices, including concerning traceability to the plot provided by a national traceability tool (SNTBG) and tools by the voluntary schemes (Gabon Ministry of Water and Forests, the Sea and the Environment, 2023), as argued by business and non-business interviewees (e.g., I42; I61; I65). However, interviewees of various types also posited that maintaining geolocation information along the value chain as timber gets transformed would pose challenges (I46; I62; I67).

According to business and non-business interviewees, the businesses were further identifying smaller adjustments needed for EUDR compliance in relation to the geolocation and human rights requirements and undertaking corresponding actions (e.g., I41; I46; I62). For example, a forest sector business representative commented that “as it's not a national legal requirement, we're not actually implementing the Free, Prior and Informed Consent” (I54). According to the interviewee, the business was now working to address this deficit. A forest sector business representative also expressed uncertainty about the EUDR forest degradation definition and its practical implications (I55). Furthermore, forest sector business representatives complained that EUDR's documentation needs are cumbersome, and that supporting compliance will bring added costs, but no real benefits compared to pre-existing EUTR compliance and voluntary certification efforts (e.g., I41; I51; I62).

A majority of timber businesses in Gabon – mostly Asian-owned and not certified – export mainly to Asia, especially China (International Trade Centre, n.d.). As commented by a forest sector business association representative, these companies are not bothered by the EUDR: “Many of the companies that don't comply with the regulations don't export to the EU, so I don't think they'll necessarily feel concerned, since they mainly export to China. (I44)” With a long-term view, NGO and forest sector business association representatives believed that some of these Asian-owned businesses, whether currently exporting to the EU or not, will want to seek EUDR compliance and EU market access, for instance through voluntary certification (I46; I49; I66). According to business and non-business interviewees, the EUDR will also trigger some companies to shift their market destination from the EU to elsewhere (e.g., I44; I45; I50).

8.4 EU

Behavioral drivers

Europe-based business actors' motivation to comply with the EUDR across the forest and agricultural sectors was largely driven by a regulative compliance-oriented logic (e.g., 175; 197; 1106). A forest sector business actor, for instance, stated that "the most important point is compliance with legal requirements" (197). Similarly, a retailer from the agricultural sector stated that their main activities after the EUDR's adoption include setting up compliance processes: "At the moment, it's about being compliant, understanding the regulation and setting up the processes in such a way that we are legally compliant. (1106)" A business association representative from the forest sector further stated that the new inspection targets and due diligence statement submission obligations will likely lead to higher awareness and compliance among forest sector business actors: "So you cannot say any more [...] 'I don't know what is this', no, you have to do at least something, so I think things will change because companies will be more aware of the fact that [the] EUDR is not only for the tropical timber importers, but it's here for everyone. (1123)" Furthermore, a representative from a research organization highlighted that some businesses may expect EUDR-like standards to emerge in other markets, which is why they already want to "future proof" their operations with EUDR compliance (183). At the same time, a forest sector retailer highlighted compliance-related economic concerns: "We don't want to be kicked out of the market by legal regulations. (194)"

Business actors also raised concerns about other non-compliant business actors (184; 194; 1123). A forest sector retailer, for instance, predicted that fraud (e.g., in product documentation) will continue and that the higher standards for compliant business actors will result in strengthening non-compliant competitors: "The bar is being set higher and higher for us, and the Chinese competitors are laughing up their sleeves and saying: 'Oh nice, how you're catapulting yourselves out of the market, you couldn't be more stupid.' (194)" Similarly, a representative from a European forest sector business association criticized inspection shortcomings for small opportunistic companies: "Sometimes you have companies that are guided by one person [who] sees opportunities somewhere in a certain country and [...] imports some timber and then [...] stops that, and those people [...] don't get inspected [which is] frustrating all the other members. (1123)"

Notably, the EUDR's new potential penalties of 4% of the company's total annual turnover were mentioned as a strong deterrence effect by both business and non-business interviewees (e.g., 182; 194; 1122). This is best illustrated by a forest sector retailer describing the 4% penalty as "quite a number" (194). Furthermore, a business association representative from the agricultural sector pointed out that non-compliance risks could result in the exclusion of smallholders without land titles: "It just becomes tricky for a company to want to include smallholders without land titles in the supply chain just because it's a big risk that the penalties

for non-compliance are very high in the EUDR. (I122)" The Commission clarified in its FAQ's that the legality requirement is considered to be fulfilled if farmers are legally allowed to farm and sell their products under national laws even in the absence of a property register and farmer IDs (European Commission, 2023). A representative from the pulp and paper industry sourcing from Brazil, on the other hand, stated that they are working on providing all the legal requirements without having to change their business model: "We already comply [...] because we do a business completely deforestation and degradation free. (I129)" Finally, business and non-business interviewees also noted that the degree to which companies feel the influence of penalties and a deterrence effect will ultimately depend on the strictness of controls and the penalties issued (e.g., I84; I86; I121).

Corporate sustainability efforts in general – and EUDR compliance strategies in particular – were also driven by economic considerations, such as ensuring continued resource availability, best illustrated by a forest sector business association representative: "We support this kind of legislation because we don't want forests to disappear because then we don't have any raw materials anymore. (I123)" Business and non-business interviewees also noted the importance of the EU market for non-EU suppliers, such as the higher price that the EU market pays for timber (e.g., I81; I82; I90). A forest sector business representative further recognized increasing demands for sustainably operating enterprises at the capital market: "[There] is quite clearly an orientation towards a [...] demand for sustainably operating companies on the capital market. (I97)" Additionally, business actors stated that they would not be able to afford being non-compliant, because the market would punish that (e.g., loss of customers and reputation) and, hence, the negative consequence for business would go beyond that of the formal EUDR penalty (I84; I85).

A Europe-based representative from the pulp and paper industry sourcing from Brazil, on the other hand, stated that EUDR compliance was not a commercial decision for their enterprise since they already comply: "It's never been a commercial decision, it's more a sustainability way of [...] doing our business decision. (I129)" Further, forest sector business association and research organization representatives noted that businesses that have previously not done investments that they now need to do for the EUDR, as well as SMEs that will likely face a disproportionate economic burden, feel more economic disincentives from EUDR compliance compared to front-runners and larger businesses (I77; I83).

Additionally, business actors explained how corporate sustainability efforts were also driven by normative factors such as public pressure through NGO naming and shaming campaigns and consumer demands for sustainably and legally produced goods (e.g., I94; I106; I122). Maintaining a good reputation, for instance, was mentioned by business actors across the forest and agricultural sector as a key concern (e.g., I121; I122; I123). This is best illustrated by a business

association representative from the forest sector: “Once you were mentioned in a newspaper by an NGO – if it’s true or not, it doesn’t matter – [...] your name is in there, and it’s bad for your reputation. (I123)” A business association representative from the agricultural sector further explained that higher-risk sectors have a longer tradition of corporate risk mitigation policies: “NGO pressure [and] consumers priorities [have] an impact [, which is] why companies have been working on deforestation-free supply chains for a long time, particularly in the palm oil sector [...] where you have the most criticism. (I122)” Similarly, a business association representative from the forest sector described how the tropical timber industry has a strong focus on preventing naming and shaming campaigns: “No one wants to be in the newspaper with a heading ‘illegally harvested timber captured in the Port of Antwerp’. (I123)” A forest sector business actor explained that public pressure is “maintained by the nature conservation industry” (I96). An additional issue motivating EUDR compliance raised by representatives of a business associations and an NGO was the European Commission’s prospective publication of non-compliant businesses (I76; I86).

At the same time, other business and non-business interviewees argued that normative pressures, such as reputational concerns or NGO campaigns, are not a relevant driver motivating EUDR compliance, particularly when it comes to smaller businesses or some EU Member States (e.g., I75; I77; I93). For instance, a forest sector business representative commented: “Yeah, at this moment, I don’t see, in Italy at least, NGO or public opinion pressure on this. They still don’t know exactly what the EUTR is. So it will take another 10 years before they understand the EUDR. (I84)”

In relation to cultural-cognitive logic, business actors across the forest and agricultural sectors mentioned certification (e.g., FSC) and company internal policies (e.g., deforestation-free policies) as corporate strategies to ensure and prove sustainability efforts (e.g., I78; I94; I106). A forest sector retailer stated, for instance, that they “want to protect the forest and [...] have a strategy [to at least certify] 100% of [their] furniture [with] FSC” (I94). Similarly, a retailer from the agricultural sector referred to the adoption of their 2021 deforestation-free strategy, which was driven by “a very intrinsic motivation, [...] which [was] of course also somehow externally driven and demanded by the customer” (I106).

Other cultural-cognitive motivations included European forest owners’ desires to inherit valuable forests to their children, as put by a forest sector association representative: “The majority of forest owners in Europe are small forest owners and families, and they naturally want to pass on their forests to their children in the same or better condition. (I128)” Other forest sector business representatives echoed similar business-internal values of forest preservation, which is also essential for long-term business sustainability (I81; I93). A representative from a Europe-based pulp and paper company sourcing from Brazil further explained their longstanding company tradition of being FSC-certified based on a strategic

company decision: “There was a very early understanding [about] how we want to do a business and how we want to position ourselves [and] we have been [FSC] partners from the first moment on. (I129)” Additionally, a business association representative from the agricultural sector highlighted that company commitments can go beyond the EUDR’s requirements by committing to broader sustainability goals, such as practicing regenerative agriculture: “The only requirement in the EUDR is compliance with national legislation [and deforestation-free requirements] but company commitments go beyond that. (I122)”

However, sole reliance on company internal sustainability commitments was criticized by representatives from the forest industry, NGO community, certifiers and knowledge providers (e.g., I85; I86; I107). This is best illustrated by a consultant stating that “the cognitive elements are certainly important for some companies, but [...] they’re really lower down the list in most cases” (I125). Similarly, a representative from an international organization described how corporate cultures also developed in response to public pressure: “Cultural yes, but the culture has very often been fed by civil society pressure. (I124)” Furthermore, a forest sector business association representative noted that while businesses may have ambitious sustainability policies in place, they do not necessarily implement them strictly (I85). Additionally, forest sector business actors expressed that businesses still had insufficient knowledge about the EUDR (e.g., I76; I78; I84).

Behavioral responses

Businesses operating and trading in the EU market across the forest and agricultural sectors were busy preparing for the EUDR’s implementation. Key activities included exchanging with and obtaining information and data from their suppliers, supporting their upstream suppliers, adjusting their due diligence systems, and hiring new staff (e.g., I77; I78; I79). Business associations supported their member businesses to prepare for the EUDR’s implementation through awareness raising and information activities (e.g., I75, I85, I22). A forest sector business association representative noted that while a few businesses were preparing on their own, most were expecting the association “to tell them what to do” (I76). Others reported that they were also updating their already existing due diligence systems that they provided as a solution to member companies. They added that there were ongoing discussions among various national timber trade associations about the adoption of a single, unified due diligence system (I77; I85). Business (association) representatives also described a range of EU business responses with a longer-term view, such as hiring more staff, auditing suppliers more frequently, intensifying stakeholder consultations, asking suppliers more for certified timber, small operators becoming traders to evade some of the EUDR requirements, and stopping sourcing from smaller suppliers (e.g., I80; I85; I93). Moreover, representatives from a research organization expected that some businesses might relocate their offices to small EU countries with presumably weaker EUDR enforcement (I82; I83)

Business actors generally welcomed the EUDR's overarching goals of addressing global deforestation but stressed a range of implementation-related concerns (e.g., 175; 1128; 1129). A forest sector retailer, for instance, described the EUDR as a “bureaucratic monster” due to the associated increase in administrative burdens and the need to develop new information technology and artificial intelligence solutions (194). Relatedly, a retailer from the agricultural sector highlighted concerns about potentially not being able to receive the required information from upstream suppliers: “We have no legal recourse [...], and the supplier may not have the means to [provide the requested information]. Perhaps in 1, 2, 3, 4 years, but certainly not in the near future. (1106).”

Furthermore, business actors across the forest and agricultural sectors criticized a lack of clarity concerning the EUDR's requirements, resulting in difficulties in preparing for the EUDR's implementation. This includes concerns about how to develop solutions with information technology service providers, uncertainties about staff needs, strategic investment decisions, and open questions about documentation needs (e.g., 197; 1106; 1122). This is best illustrated by a European business association representative from the agricultural sector stating that “the regulation is not very clear when it comes to the specifics [and that] a lot of companies across the sectors are very nervous about this” (1122). The representative reported a strong willingness to comply while stressing business actors' dissatisfaction with the EUDR due to cooperation challenges with the European Commission and competent authorities (e.g., difficulty to receive answers) (1122). Similarly, a business association representative from the forest sector stated that they “really want to do what's necessary, but it's not clear yet what [they] need to do” (1123).

Business actor representatives from the forest and agricultural sector criticized the lack of an interface with the European Commission's information system, stressing the impossibility of manually uploading their due diligence statements (e.g., 184; 194; 197). A forest sector business association representative involved in testing the information system reported about difficulties in connecting it to other existing systems: “It's mostly [...] manual entr[ies] and this is just like [...] going back to [the] 80s. (1121)” Uncertainties about how to fulfill the due diligence statement submission obligations also made it difficult for companies to estimate implementation costs, as explained by a representative from a European forest sector business association raising issues about manually inputting data into the European Commission's information system: “with the current system, it's [...] impossible. You need to hire a lot of extra staff in order to be able to fill in all the data. (1123)” The Commission has subsequently developed an Application Programme Interface to facilitate data upload and management for which conformance testing was underway in June 2024 (European Commission, 2024b).

Business actors further questioned the EUDR's proportionality, best illustrated by a forest sector retailer: "Just because [of] a few cases [...] in Romania [...], we are not shooting at mosquitoes with cannons anymore, but also with nuclear weapons. This [traders' obligation to check operators] is completely out of proportion. (I94)" Similarly, a forest sector business association representative questioned the value of demanding geolocation information from European timber: "I'm not convinced [that] it's the right way to [ask] all companies to provide all geolocation data, even for the timber that's harvested here in Europe. (I123)" A business association representative from the agricultural sector highlighted difficulties in achieving a 100% implementation considering the complexity of global commodity supply chains and asked a series of open questions around implications and penalties for potentially not being able to provide information about some plots of land: "You can imagine how maybe out of thousands of plots [...] it was not possible to get the documentation X and Y [for two plots]. It was challenging for the smallholder. [...] So what do you do there? And [...] are you penalized for that? (I122)"

Additional key concerns evolved around the European Commission's delay in developing the country benchmarking system, and Member States' delays in designating national competent authorities and enforcement capacities (e.g., I121; I123; I128). In light of these challenges, a representative from a forest sector business association reported about industry demands to delay the EUDR's implementation (I128).

Sector-specific challenges include supply chain segregation challenges in soy value chains as mass balance systems are not accepted under the EUDR unless compliance can be ensured for all mixed commodities. Furthermore, soy credit systems are not compatible with the EUDR's geolocation requirement due to the decoupling of financial and physical flows. A European business association representative from the agricultural sector explained that business actors started investing in physically segregating their supply chains: "The physical volumes themselves have to be from plots that were deforestation free and [meet] a wide series of criteria. And the problem with soy is that we don't have the infrastructure to accommodate for that. (I122)" The representative raised concerns that investments into new segregation infrastructure will not necessarily result in lower deforestation rates "because [...] you're still just getting the deforestation-free volumes going into the EU" (I122).

In the timber sector, a European forest sector business association representative explained that forest owners were already responsible for implementing the EUTR and highlighted their familiarity with providing information about legality requirements (I128). Furthermore, a forest sector business association representative reported that compliance is comparatively easier for European businesses due to their experience with the EUTR and lower deforestation risks in Europe: "In [...] Europe, there is no deforestation [...] in the same context as in other parts of the world. So there is no reason [...] not to comply. (I121)" However,

business representatives from the forest sector also raised concerns about providing information about the new deforestation-free requirements, and particularly the geolocation requirement (e.g., I94; I121; I128): “The biggest new thing that came with [the] deforestation regulation is this geolocation [requirement] and at the same time it’s the biggest challenge. (I121)” A forest sector business association representative also voiced concerns about the current impossibility to get accurate geolocation data from China due to political reasons (I76). That being said, forest sector business representatives claimed that obtaining geolocation data especially from producers in countries that have digitized timber traceability systems, like Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon, will not be a major issue (I77; I84; I93).

A forest sector business organization representative further pointed to the possibility that private forest owners in Europe may decide to stop managing their forests to avoid potential illegalities (i.e., deforestation after the EUDR’s cut-off date) in the case of not being able to reforest their land (e.g., due to financial shortcomings) (I97), even though the EUDR’s definition of deforestation is focused on the conversion of forests to agricultural use (Art. 2) and alternatives (e.g., managing natural regeneration) exist to reforestation. Another representative from a forest sector business association raised concerns about costs associated with establishing a new due diligence system, which could also result in forest owners deciding to stop managing their forests (I128). The representative reported a Commission cost estimate of a one-off cost of 5000€ - 90.000€, stating that this “would simply not be worth it for the vast majority of forest owners” (I128). Further concerns related to the forest degradation-free requirement and human rights and other social aspects (e.g., labor rights) of EUDR implementation, as business actors indicated unclarity as to what these will practically mean for their operations (e.g., I77; I84; I85).

In the pulp and paper sector, key challenges include the traceability to the plot of land, best illustrated by a business association representative from the forest sector stating that “it may then be more attractive to source your material from huge areas, because you only need 200 plots of land to produce a book instead of 300,000” (I28). Notably, this is a key challenge for European enterprises sourcing softwood chips from various private forest owners compared to the well-prepared pulp and paper industry in Brazil sourcing entire trees from large plantations (I29). A Europe-based representative from a pulp and paper business sourcing from Brazil highlighted that they are mostly concerned with technicalities about how to deliver existing data: “It’s not about not having the data and not showing where the pulp is coming from [...] it’s more [about] how to deliver the data to the competent authorities through the [information] system. (I129)” The representative also voiced criticism about the EUDR’s country benchmarking system assigning commodity unspecific risk ratings by highlighting their longstanding preparedness under the EUTR: “Maybe [these regulatory requirements are new for] other sectors or other commodities [but] why should we be punished for that? (I129)”

9 DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Observing the findings across the different value chain regions and commodities, certain patterns become evident. The economic logic emerges as an important logic in all contexts, which means that EUDR compliance is usually a commercial decision for businesses. On the supply side (Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon), the EU is perceived as a profitable market and most businesses that already have commercial relations with EU buyers would want to ensure their continued EU market access, even with the higher EUDR standards. As part of business transactions, these businesses feel the EU market requirements (i.e., the EUDR standards) through demands (i.e., EUDR due diligence) by the businesses operating and trading in the EU market. This is essential, as it is through these due diligence processes that EUDR hard rules (regulative logic) become tangible for non-EU businesses. For timber and wood pulp, higher prices paid by the EU market were also highlighted. At the same time, other domestic and export markets (e.g., in Asia) for the commodities exist with apparent good or satisfactory profit margins, so that businesses also target these markets – partly or exclusively – for economic reasons. The EUDR was also seen as creating restrictions and economic burdens for accessing the EU market, which may lead some to abandoning the market. On the demand side (the EU), slightly different issues of wanting to ensure continued natural resource availability and market demand for sustainably operating businesses were brought up. Here, counter-arguments to the economic logic were also made, such as that EUDR compliance is not primarily a commercial but rather regulative-driven decision, highlighting compliance-related economic burdens (e.g., for resource-constrained SMEs and small private forest owners, retailers handling large volumes of products). This is also linked to the regulative logic, as businesses would not want to become excluded from a market because of regulatory reasons.

The regulative logic was ascribed mixed influence depending on the context. On the demand side, it appeared the key logic, since the EUDR legal obligations directly apply only to businesses operating and trading in the EU market. Accordingly, a felt deterrence effect from the EUDR's penalties was a key factor driving these businesses' desire to ensure compliance with the new regulation. However, our findings also highlight worries that the regulative logic could apply unevenly to businesses within the EU due to, for example, smaller businesses escaping the controls when most enforcement attention is put on large businesses. Another concern expressed was that the regulative logic could be undermined altogether if the controls and penalties will not be strictly enforced, for instance due to lacking capacities by EU Member State competent authorities. On the supply side, the regulative logic was not similarly present owing to the fact that the EUDR legal obligations do not directly apply to businesses outside the EU. Specifically, the regulative logic was comparatively weaker in Brazil and wholly lacking in Cameroon and Gabon. A possible explanation for the difference lies in the commodities: soy and wood pulp value

chains are highly vertically integrated across the supply and demand sides through trading companies that control both the export and import. This means that possible penalties for the importer in the EU would indirectly be felt also by the Brazil-based exporter, since they can be part of the same company group. Therefore, regulative concerns already weigh on the export side in the decision to comply with the EUDR. In timber trade, however, the value chains consist of exporters and importers that are usually completely separate from each other. As such, potential EUDR penalties are not similarly considered on the supply side.

The normative logic appeared rather evenly with a moderate influence across all the value chains and geographical regions. A key point was the importance of reputation (protection) for businesses. While societal pressure, for instance through NGO campaigns, was assessed as rather weak in all the supply side countries, its influence was perceived more strongly on the demand side. It was also pointed out that such normative pressures are less effective in value chain contexts where the supply side is characterized by weaker governance (cf. regulative logic) or when the demand side market is not responsive to environmental concerns (cf. economic logic). Reputational concerns can also be a lesser consideration for businesses that are not stock companies (and do not have shareholders to respond to) or are not exposed to the public in the same way that consumer-facing and large businesses and brands can be, which highlights the interconnectedness of the normative and economic logics in relation to reputational concerns.

Across the value chains, the cultural-cognitive logic was described as having overall the lowest influence in driving businesses' behavioral responses to the EUDR, although the logic appeared more prominent on the demand side than the supply side. For example, while some businesses have internal policies related to the environment and sustainability that can even aim higher than the EUDR (e.g., regenerative agricultural practices), it was noted that not all businesses have such policies, that their implementation can be lacking, and that typically such internal policies and values are rather the result of external normative influences, market-related economic interests, or regulatory requirements. Additionally, it was observed that while actors were aware of the EUDR, knowledge about it was still insufficient among businesses, which could be due to lacking implementation and enforcement related information from the European Commission and because of the EUDR's relative recency at the time of the interviews for this study. We also observed misunderstandings about the EUDR among interviewees.

Some patterns can also be identified in relation to businesses' behavioral responses to the EUDR. In all the value chains, preparations by businesses for EUDR implementation were ongoing. Discontent exists in all value chains with the perceived highly bureaucratic nature of the EUDR and expected cumbersome compliance procedures. For instance, businesses are expected to face various challenges related to the EUDR's geolocation and traceability requirements,

ranging from financial to technical to political. As a result, it appears that businesses will try to simplify their value chains, cutting out intermediaries, indirect suppliers, and small market actors outside the EU who cannot provide the requested information or who may otherwise complicate compliance. Generally speaking, SMEs and other small market actors are expected to face more difficulties or higher economic burden in complying with the EUDR (in the EU) or producing EUDR compliant products (outside the EU). Moreover, existing divisions in value chains, where some supply side market actors have access to the EU market and others are mainly connected to domestic or other export markets with lower legality and deforestation-free standards, may become reinforced.

These developments – and our findings in general – raise important questions and concerns for the role of the EU in its sustainability efforts in supply side countries and the potential effectiveness of the EUDR, once its implementation begins. The higher EUDR requirements could make the EU more of an exclusive market to which fewer supply side actors have access, particularly those that are already (mostly) aligned with the EUDR standards. A particular challenge posed by an EUDR-induced, strengthened division in value chains is that market actors who could no longer access the EU market due to the increased EUDR standards would tend to shift their sales to other markets with lower standards. Moreover, in the soy value chain, for example, multinational businesses can also segregate their supply of EUDR compliant and non-compliant products. Such developments could reduce the EU's market potential of leveraging change in supply side countries. Also, associated spillover effects could result in lower overall effectiveness of the EUDR (Meyfroidt et al., 2020).²

Furthermore, it is a known challenge that as a demand side instrument, the EUDR's potential to leverage change globally can be limited by the market share that the EU holds of global imports in a commodity (Bastos Lima & Schilling-Vacaflor, 2024; Vasconcelos et al., 2024). In this context, a possible avenue for enhancing the effectiveness of the EUDR even in such contexts would be if governments of third countries (e.g., in Asia) started raising their standards to the level of the EUDR, thus resulting in a so-called “Brussels Effect”, or regulatory “race to the top”, diffusing the advanced EUDR standards to other major demand markets (Bradford, 2012, 2020). However, this may be unlikely to happen at least in the short term (Bastos Lima & Schilling-Vacaflor, 2024; Vasconcelos et al., 2024). A more likely avenue could be if some businesses in third countries started adhering to and conducting EUDR-aligned due diligence (even without changes in the respective national regulatory context), as hinted in at least some of our findings.

Moreover, our findings showed that, while economic logic is prime for non-EU businesses seeking EU market access (and ensuring their products are EUDR compliant), being a trade restricting policy (Muradian et al., 2025), the EUDR

² Spillover effects will be dealt with in greater detail in CLEVER Deliverable 5.2.

lacks positive economic incentives, which these businesses were missing. Thus, it would be key for the EUDR and associated supportive measures to tap more into the economic logic of businesses' thinking by creating positive economic incentives to motivate further businesses (particularly outside the EU) to improve their practices or to transition their systems for EUDR compliance and seek EU market access. This could be especially beneficial for SMEs and other small market actors, who face proportionally higher costs and challenges in ensuring their products are EUDR compliant and could end up being excluded from EU-bound value chains. A precedent of the EU committing to providing market-related incentives lies in the Voluntary Partnership Agreements negotiated between the EU and timber producing countries that have stipulated market-related incentives, such as promotional campaigns for timber and timber products, from the EU side (e.g., European Commission, 2010). Presently, the EU and Member States are stepping up their assistance to non-EU countries, with, for example, establishment of the Team Europe Initiative on deforestation-free value chains, which focusses on forming and maintaining inclusive partnerships with third countries. It also includes a technical facility to support non-EU countries with the EUDR.³ The EU is also developing Forest Partnerships as part of its wider commitments.⁴ However, the current scale and level of support is unlikely to be sufficient.

In this context, the effectiveness of the EUDR will also in part depend on whether EU businesses follow the obligations and spirit of the regulation, particularly around supporting smallholders through capacity building and investments as part of their risk mitigation, as outlined in the EUDR (Art. 11). This also speaks to the wider importance of the regulative logic for EU businesses. Being the main behavioral driver to them, it will be crucial for EU Member States to establish sufficient capacities for their competent authorities to perform their role effectively and for the competent authorities to ensure strict monitoring and enforcement of the EUDR evenly across the EU. Otherwise, as highlighted in our findings, the essential influence of the regulative logic could be undermined, and EU businesses could neglect or circumvent their obligations under the EUDR.

Our findings indicate less leverage of the normative and cultural-cognitive logics over influencing business behavior in response to the EUDR, except for certain businesses that are sensitive to reputational concerns or who have sustainability high on their internal agenda. Concerning cultural-cognitive logic, it will also be important for businesses to improve their knowledge and understanding of the EUDR to enable appropriate and informed responses to it. Here, the EU is tasked to effective and timely communication about the EUDR to actors inside and outside the EU.

³ <https://zerodeforestationhub.eu/>

⁴ https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/climate-environment-and-energy/forests_en

Finally, previous research has applied the framework of the four behavioral logics in the context of EU-based businesses' responses to a similar EU regulation (the EUTR) (Köthke and Sotirov, 2024). In the present research, we successfully applied the framework for analyzing both EU-internal and external businesses' responses to an EU regulation. We also showed that it is crucial to understand the interconnectedness of the four behavioral logics, as in practice they in many cases do not operate in isolation. This research further contributes to existing literature analyzing regulatory compliance behavior in the context of FERCs, such as timber ((Acheampong & Maryudi, 2020; Berock & Ongolo, 2019; Boakye, 2018; Köthke, 2020; Köthke & Sotirov, 2024; Mayers et al., 2009; Nathan et al., 2018; Tegegne et al., 2022)). Our study comes with a limitation particularly in relation to behavioral responses, since the EUDR was not yet implemented during the study's data collection. Hence, interviewees' stated responses to the EUDR may not fully reflect what they *de facto* will do. Future research could inspect behavioral responses and drivers of businesses after the EUDR implementation and enforcement begins, including by expanding the value chain scope to cover other commodities and/or countries. Related research could also look into how ex-ante expected leakage/ spillover mechanisms (cf. Deliverable 5.2) may play out during EUDR implementation. Beyond business responses, another interesting avenue for research would be to explore practical EUDR implementation and enforcement behavior of EU Member States and how non-EU countries respond to EUDR implementation.

10 PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This report produced an understanding of how value chain actors respond to policies and governance mechanisms – taking the case of business actors' responses to the EUDR as an empirical case. First, the report mapped five focal value chains (Brazil-EU soy, timber, and wood pulp, and Cameroon-EU and Gabon-EU timber). Second, the report identified the drivers that influence business actors' behavior and described business actors' behavioral responses to the EUDR in preparation for its implementation. Through this, the report generated an understanding of key behavioral drivers of business compliance with EU law inside and outside the EU and drew lessons on the potential effectiveness of EUDR implementation.

The complementary Deliverable 5.2 will analyze more specifically businesses' strategies in response to the EUDR and what leakage and other spillover effects might result from those. Deliverable 5.3 will synthesize the insights from Work Packages 4 and 5 and gauge the plausibility of effects from the EUDR on biodiversity.

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